

UNISECO

UNDERSTANDING & IMPROVING THE
SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRO-ECOLOGICAL
FARMING SYSTEMS IN THE EU

Deliverable Report D8.3

Interim Report on Communication, Dissemination and Impact of Project Activities

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ACRONYMS

AEFS	Agro-ecological farming systems
AKH	Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
MAP-NEF	Multi-Actor Platform Networking Facility
PAG	Project Advisory Group

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable gives an overview of the communication and dissemination (COMDISS) activities of the UNISECO consortium in the first 18 months of the project duration.

Communication-dissemination activities are under continuous monitoring of the WP8 Dissemination work package leader GEO.

The objectives of project communication and project result dissemination activities are:

- to maximise the visibility of the project to the intended target groups from the agricultural, environmental and rural business community, stakeholders, administrations, and scientific community;
- to facilitate outreach and engagement of key actors, and potential users of, and contributors to the knowledge hub;
- to disseminate project outcomes to stakeholders, key actors and end-users;
- to maximise exploitation of project results and coordinate preparations for post-project exploitation.

Communication and dissemination activities are carefully planned, continuously implemented and regularly monitored during the whole duration of the project. All project partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities.

Communication and dissemination activities are carried out according to Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan (Deliverable D8.1, Balazs *et al.*, 2018) which analyses the dissemination target groups and match them with the most appropriate channels, key messages for communication, and external partners with whom to cooperate on co-dissemination whenever relevant. It is annually updated with contributions from all partners.

One representative of each consortium partner team was assigned as Communication-Dissemination-Exploitation Officer (COMDISS Officers) after the project meeting in month 7.

Communication and dissemination (COMDISS Officers) continuously keep records of partner's Communication and dissemination activities in a template developed for this purpose and upload these internal partner communication and dissemination progress reports every project quarter to the file repository system of the project on the [Thünen Extranet](#). With regular intervals BEF-LT, leader of Task 8.2 Joint dissemination activities, summarizes and analyses partner's communication and dissemination efforts by communication channels and modes of dissemination which is then presented at meetings of the Executive Board and at project meetings. Furthermore, quarterly online meetings of COMDISS Officers are organised and serve the purpose of continuous planning, supervision and improvement of communication and dissemination activities.

UNISECO is pursuing a multi-actor approach at EU-level and at case study level (also with involvement of national level actors) to involve stakeholders at the earliest stages of project scoping and design as well as throughout the project. This has included the identification of challenges relating to the types of factors land managers consider when planning for the future, and current and prospective sources and routes of information by stakeholder groups, and the direct project engagement of partners such as WWF-Romania, and ELO, as well as sub-contracting of stakeholder champions in case studies.

A multi-platform outreach approach to dissemination brings UNISECO results to the marketplace, highlighting why and how outcomes will benefit target audiences. All non-confidential products generated are made freely and openly available through multiple channels. An essential activity is the design and running of a Europe-wide dissemination campaign with the aims of:

- creating stakeholder awareness of the case studies and the project as a whole;

- disseminating results;
- developing networks of practitioners in agro-ecological farming systems;
- creating the basis for a significant legacy of project outcomes;
- disseminating success stories of achievements of UNISECO to promote adoption of the approaches to sharing knowledge, add value, lever resources and promote project innovations amongst end-user and stakeholder communities in the agri-food value chain.

This document analyses the COMDISS activities of the consortium carried out in the first 18 months of the project. It sets out the impact assessment of

- i) communication activities / channels including the project website, Multi-Actor Platforms, social media channels, newsletters, communication through European Commission and other channels;
- ii) dissemination materials and publications;
- iii) external peer-to-peer exchanges;
- iv) Key Performance indicators related to communication and dissemination activities.

1. IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

1.1. Communication and Dissemination Channels

A set of specific communication-dissemination channels were set up at the beginning of the project based on the principles of:

- adaptability (to address the project's research themes and stakeholder communities),
- flexibility (a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges),
- tailored messages in appropriate language,
- exploitation of synergies (cross-fertilisation with existing communication and dissemination activities).

These principles are to ensure that the project can fully exploit its strengths and opportunities, while limiting and managing its weakness and threats.

1.1.1. Project website

The communication-dissemination of the project is organised using several different channels. One of the main communication-dissemination channels is the project website: uniseco-project.eu. The website was set up at the beginning of the project and went online in August 2018, therefore Google analytics data are available from 1st September 2018.

The UNISECO project website is a key tool for communicating information about project activities, news and events, as well as to convey results to a wide range of target groups including farmers; authorities and administrations at different geographic levels; agri-food value chain actors; science, innovation, advisory and capacity building actors; NGOs, civic society organisations, local community representatives; consumers; and the media. The website was created in line with the visual identity and is continuously maintained by GEO with contributions from all partners.

The website contains a section on 'News and events', where the most relevant news about the project and important issues are published. The website also contains:

- information about the UNISECO project and its work packages,
- project partners,
- Project Advisory Group (PAG),
- case studies in the partner countries,
- project resources (publications, newsletters, videos, deliverables, etc.),
- and other useful links.

An image of the website homepage (Welcome page) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Welcome page of the UNISECO website: www.uniseco-project.eu with an integrated Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub

The core sections of the project website are provided in the English language. Information about certain topics is also provided in languages of all of the project partners (English, Czech, Finish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Romanian, Spanish and Swedish).

Access to the project website is monitored and reported upon using the Google Analytics toolbox. The number of website hits, which is Project Key Performance Indicator 7, was 6,043 for the period from September 2018 to the end of October 2019. This compares with the initial target over the project lifetime of 800. A summary of information about access to the www site follows.

Number of users

The number of users of the website grew each month since the website went live in September 2018. In the first 18 months there were 3,154 users. The biggest number of users was in March 2019, which coincided with the first workshop of the EU-level MAP and the publication of the first project Deliverables on the project website. An illustration of the number of users accessing the website through the first 18 months is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Graphic of growth of UNISECO website users (1st September 2018 to 31st October 2019) (Source: Google Analytics).

Of the users of the website, 84.3% are new visitors, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Number of users of the UNISECO website, new and returning (1st September 2018 to 31st October 2019) (Source: Google Analytics).

Sessions

There was a total number of 6,043 sessions occurred in the 18 months September 2018 to October 2019. On average, a user visited the website almost twice (1.92) and a session lasted 3 minutes and 28 seconds (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Website statistics (1st September 2018 to 31st October 2019) (Source: Google Analytics).

Page views

The total number of pages viewed was 17,275 (including repeated views of a single page) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Graphic of UNISECO page views (1st September 2018 to 31st October 2019).

1.1.2. Multi-Actor Platforms and the MAP Networking Facility Forums

The UNISECO transdisciplinary framework comprises the two levels of Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), one at EU-level and one for each of the 15 case studies. Key intersection points for co-learning and co-construction of new insights and outputs through participatory processes with the Multi-Actor Platforms exist within research and dissemination efforts (Irvine *et al.*, 2019). This two-level approach has created a structure which has enabled timely engagement with relevant actors across the various phases of UNISECO's work packages (WPs) in the first reporting period to foster the transdisciplinary and co-construction approach central to UNISECO.

The EU-level Multi-Actor Platforms consists of key actors with an EU-level perspective and a stake in European policies and agro-ecological transitions of farming and rural areas. This includes EU-wide environmental NGOs, sector organisations, and the European Commission.

The involvement of members of the Multi-Actor Platforms occurred through:

- i) The contribution of different sources of information, knowledge and insight. Examples are the co-construction with case study MAPs of governance networks with actors that impact on agro-ecological transitions in the case studies, done in 8 workshops and 78 interviews with case study MAP members.
- ii) The identification and refinement of specific direction and content for methods and tools. Examples are the consultation of EU-level MAP members in the selection of case studies in the early stages of the project, the development of the spatially explicit online tool (SESSIT) of the knowledge hub and the co-construction of scenarios for the territorial level modelling with EU-level and case study MAP members at two workshops in March and May 2019.
- iii) Discussion of, and feedback on, intermediate and end-of-project research findings. Examples are the in-depth discussions with EU-level and case study MAP members of the agro-ecological farming typology, case study findings and results of the policy analysis at case study workshops and the project workshop in Helsinki in May 2019
- iv) Challenging the validity of research outputs. This role will be greater in the second reporting period.
- v) The co-construction and evaluation of the robustness of management strategies and policy recommendations. This role will be greater in the second reporting period, in Tasks 3.4 and 5.4.

- vi) Reflective review of the MAP approach incorporated into UNISECO. This was done with members of the MAPs, and amongst project partners, after annual meetings based on the monitoring and evaluation approach developed in Task 7.3.

An aim of UNISECO is to promote group learning processes and co-creation of knowledge with actors and stakeholders in Multi-Actor Platforms. These processes are through physical interactions (such as workshops and focus group discussions at European Union, national and local levels), and an on-line service of the website. This on-line service uses the virtual discussion boards called the UNISECO Multi Actor Platform Networking Facility (MAP NEF) at <https://uniseco-project.eu/map-nef> (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The Multi Actor Platform Networking Facility home page.

The Multi Actor Platform Networking Facility (MAP NEF) provides access to a space for networking and knowledge exchange amongst the members of the MAPs on topics in relation to agro-ecological transitions and the sustainability of European agriculture. It also serves as a tool for informing members of the MAPs about the project processes and developments and actual questions and challenges, providing a forum for replies, opinions and recommendations. Accessing the MAP-NEF during the lifetime of the project is possible based on invitation only and with specific login credentials.

The MAP NEF is a discussion forum board (Figure 7) organized into various Discussion Forums. A Discussion Forum can cover a major topic related to the project within which any particular practical issues can be further discussed beyond the face-to-face discussions. Each discussion forum has an associated discussion Forum Manager, a member of the project consortium who is in charge of driving and moderating the discussions of the respective forum. The MAP NEF Forum will be introduced to MAP members at the project meeting and workshop with EU-level and case study MAP members as well as members of the PAG in Basel, Switzerland, in November 2019.

Figure 7. View of the MAP NEF discussion forum board, listing the available discussion topics.

1.1.3. UNISECO Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub

Progressively, the upper part of the first page of the classic project website will be converted into a multi-lingual exploitation space of the UNISECO Knowledge Hub. A router function will direct users to the emerging project results, arranged into sub-websites, linking to the main exploitation tools of UNISECO. This is designed to engage actors in the whole value chain by answering the main challenge questions that are of most concern for the target audience categories. The frame of the Knowledge Hub was launched in month 6 (October 2018).

1.1.4. Communication on partner websites

Partners use their own organisation websites as communication channels. All partners that have separate websites have uploaded basic information about UNISECO project in English and the

relevant national language. Partners also use their webpages news sections to announce the news about the project (e.g. release of the newsletters).

1.1.5. Social media channels

Communication and dissemination activities are actively carried out through project social media channels. A LinkedIn company page is used to reach the professional audience, and Twitter is aimed at reaching both professionals and the general public. Figure 8 shows the home page of the UNISECO Twitter account. Partners use personal organisation accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) to carry out communication and dissemination activities.

Posts in UNISECO social media channels revolve around agroecology, sustainable farming, studies on agriculture, sustainable food, new technologies in farming, and other ecological solutions. The social media channels are also used to promote conferences, workshops and events which were organised by the UNISECO project, or in which his has taken part, and to raise awareness about the progress in case studies and other UNISECO tasks.

A template has been provided for news items and social media posts. All partners can contribute by providing news items for social media channels. Responsibility for social media channels lies with the UNISECO Executive Board and is executed by the leaders of Work Package 8, GEO and BEF-LT.

1.1.5.1. Twitter analytics

Figure 8. Page of the UNISECO Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/ProjectUniseco>.

Access to the project social media channels is monitored and reported upon using the tools provided by each channel. The number of followers on Twitter and LinkedIn is Project Key Performance Indicator 8. As of 31st October 2019, the number of Followers on Twitter was 300, which compares to the target for the entire project period of 200. Of the 260 Tweets from the UNISECO account, there were 280 Likes. UNISECO follows 491 other Twitter accounts, including those of other relevant EU projects (e.g. LIFT, TRUE, DIVERSIFY, SIMRA, COASTAL). This compares with the initial target over the project lifetime of 800. A summary of information about access to the website follows.

The UNISECO Twitter account is followed by European Union accounts (e.g. EU CORDIS, EU Environment, ENRD Contact Point, EIP-Agri Service Point), H2020 projects (e.g. CONTRACT 2.0, EU Environment, SCENT_EU, IoF2020, SUFISA, PLAID, MINDSTEP, BRESOV_EU, SMARTCHAIN_EU, LANDMARK, SURE-FARM and LIFT) and projects financed through other EU research programmes such as LIFE (e.g. LIFE Fluvial). Key stakeholders from Europe and further afield also follow the project (e.g. EIP-Agri Lower Saxony, Organic Sweden, RISE foundation, Eco_Agriculture and Mid Atlantic Permaculture).

Table 1 contains values for metrics relating to the UNISECO Twitter account.

Table 1. Analysis of metrics of tweet activity.

Metrics	Number	Explanation
Total number of original tweets	147	Number of Tweets from the UNISECO Twitter account
Impressions	143,961	Number of times UNISECO Tweets on were viewed on Twitter
Engagements	1,577	Number of times there were interactions with UNISECO Tweets
Likes	437	Number of times people liked a UNISECO tweet
URL clicks	334	Number of clicks on a URL or card in UNISECO tweets
Media views	189	Number of view of media provided through UNSIECO tweets
Retweets	231	Number of times UNISECO tweets were retweeted
Detail expands	202	Number of times the details of UNISECO tweets were viewed in full
Hashtag clicks	40	Number of times hashtags in UNISECO tweets were clicked

Top tweets

Information is posted on Twitter twice a week (Wednesdays and Fridays). During the first 18 months of the project there were 147 posts tweeted. The top project tweet was posted in January 2019. It was about the 1st projects newsletter issued and got 3,070 impressions (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Image of the top tweet from the UNISECO Twitter account.

Top follower

The account with the highest follower count that follows the UNISECO project is EU Environment, which has 82,300 followers (as of November 2019).

Follower audiences

The UNISECO account is followed by slightly more men (54%) than women (46%).

The followers of the UNISECO Twitter account are from several different countries. The highest number of visitors are from Belgium (mainly Brussels), the United Kingdom and Spain. The proportion of followers for the top 10 countries is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Twitter followers of UNISECO, by country.

1.1.5.2. LinkedIn analytics

The project company page is shown in Figure 11. The number of visitors do not represent the actual results of the LinkedIn account. The account that was created in the beginning of the project, but had to be renewed 1st January 2019 due to legal changes at LinkedIn. As a consequence all of the details of links for the first 8 months of the project were progress and had to be recreated. The numbers provided in this report relate to the 10 months of activities from 1st January 2019 to 31st October 2019.

Figure 11. Project LinkedIn company page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/uniseco-project/>).

Figures 12 shows the distribution of page views of the LinkedIn company account through 2019, and Figure 13 the engagement as organic impressions or for updates to page content.

Figure 12. Total number of page views and unique visitors over time (1st January 2019 to 31st October 2019).

Figure 13. Aggregated engagement metrics for organic content and updates (1st January 2019 to 31st October 2019).

As of 31st October 2019 there are 64 followers of the UNISECO project company account in LinkedIn. Figure 14 shows the number of new follower per day for the period from 1st January to 31st October 2019.

Figure 14. Number of new LinkedIn followers (1st January 2019 to 31st October 2019).

The followers of the UNISECO LinkedIn account are from several countries (Figure 15). Most visitors come from Belgium (mainly Brussels), Hungary, and Italy (mainly Rome) and Switzerland.

Top locations

	Followers	% of Followers
Brussels Area, Belgium	9	20%
Hungary area	4	8.89%
Rome Area, Italy	3	6.67%
Zürich Area, Switzerland	3	6.67%
Pamplona Area, Spain	2	4.44%
Nijmegen Area, Netherlands	1	2.22%
District Brno-City, Czech Republic	1	2.22%
Edmonton, Canada Area	1	2.22%
Xi'an, Shaanxi, China	1	2.22%
Burlington, Vermont Area	1	2.22%

Figure 15. Aggregated demographics of LinkedIn members who follow the page.

Information on LinkedIn is posted twice per week (Wednesdays and Fridays). The top 3 posts on the UNISECO LinkedIn page were unique posts about the progress of the project obtaining 150, 139 and 138 impressions respectively (Figure 16). The most popular post was about the UNISECO stakeholder workshop in Helsinki, Finland, with participation of experts from FAO, EFNCP, INRA, Agroecology Europe, the LIFT project and key actors from UNISECO case studies. The second most popular post was the visit to the “Palopuro agroecological symbiosis”, Finland, which is a model of a local food production with a cooperation of farms, food processors and local energy company. The third most popular post was about a participatory workshop with local actors at the Landwirtschaftskammer in Nienburg/Weser as a part of the German case study.

Figure 16. Images from the 3 most popular posts on the UNISECO LinkedIn page.

1.1.6. Communication on partner social media channels

Project partners use their own organisation social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) as communication channels. Partners also use their social media to announce the news about the project, for example release of the newsletters and to highlight their national cases and other relevant stories.

1.1.7. On-line repositories

1.1.7.1. Researchgate project page

The UNISECO project page was opened on ResearchGate (RG) (Figure 17). This professional network for scientists and researchers is used by 15 million members from all over the world to share, discover, and discuss research. The networks mission is to connect the world of science and make research open to all. Regular updates with newsletters and project deliverables have been added to the UNISECO Researchgate page.

Figure 17. The UNISECO Researchgate page.

1.1.7.2. Zenodo project page

The UNISECO community page was opened on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/uniseco-h2020/>. The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the European Commission to support their Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for European Commission funded research. In line with the Data Management Plan (Schwarz and Miller, 2018) Zenodo will be used in the later stages of the project to provide open access to project results and databases.

1.1.8. Newsletters

The electronic newsletter is one of the project's communication-dissemination channels. The newsletter is published every 6 months and includes the most recent news from the project and different collaborations (see Appendix 4.2). In the First Reporting Period, two newsletters were published, both of which are available for download from the Resources section of the website: <https://uniseco-project.eu/resources>.

Figure 18. (a) The 1st project newsletter; (b) promotion of the 1st Project Newsletter on the UNISECO Twitter account

The 1st UNISECO Project Newsletter was published in in December 2018 (Figure 18a), and was promoted by other communication channels, such as the project Twitter account (Figure 18b). It consists of insights to meetings and other events at which the UNISECO project was presented, and information about the purpose of the UNISECO Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub and the Multi-actor Platform Networking Facility. It included an invitation to readers to explore what UNISECO can offer, where information can be found, how to participate in the project, and how they can have their say about the issues being discussed, and information about upcoming tasks and emerging results in UNISECO. There was also information about another EU project which is funded under the same research call, H2020 LIFT, with which UNISECO is cooperating.

The 2nd UNISECO project newsletter was issued and promoted in July 2019 (Figure 19). It consisted of information what the project is about and the progress made since the 1st newsletter. Readers could find about how the consortium marked the 1st anniversary with of the project at the 1st Annual Meeting and Stakeholder Workshop in Helsinki, Finland. In the 2nd newsletter they could also obtain information about the latest developments in the project, the latest deliverables produced, and where and how the partners are networking.

Figure 19. Promotion of the 2nd project newsletter.

To promote the new issues of the newsletter, an announcement about the release and readers to subscribe was published on the News section of the project website and through social media channels. The invitation was sent to all project partners for them to publish on their organization's web sites and social media accounts.

The total number of newsletter subscribers is 130 as of 30 October 2019.

The 3rd newsletter will be issued at the beginning of 2020. The 6-monthly newsletters are compiled by the BEF-LT (leader of Task 8.2) and edited by GEO with contributions of all partners.

1.1.9. Videos and films

During the First Reporting Period 5 videos (Appendix 4.11) were prepared and published on the UNISECO project website under the Resources section. These are:

- The introductory video “What are the expectations of the European Commission towards the UNISECO H2020 project?” was prepared and published. Explanation by Andrea Furlan, EC DG AGRI Officer, Member of the UNISECO EU-level MAP (<https://bit.ly/363HcY6>).
- What are the expectations of the European Commission towards the UNISECO H2020 project? Gaëtan Dubois, policy officer from DG AGRI, Research and Innovation Unit explains (<https://bit.ly/2qzLuWE>).
- What are the expectations of the European Commission towards the UNISECO H2020 project? Peter Goddard, Honorary Fellow of the James Hutton Institute, UK, UNISECO Project Advisory Group Member explains (<https://bit.ly/2MGP8H6>).
- What is the most significant social science challenge for the uptake of agro-ecological approaches? Hilde Bjørkhaug, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway, UNISECO Project Advisory Group Member explains (<https://bit.ly/35VZdHL>).
- Hungarian case study: liquid fertiliser injector machine in no-till corn production (<https://bit.ly/2NaGYFG>).

1.1.10. Communication through European Commission Channels

Communication channels supported by the European Commission are used for news about events and results. UNISECO is proactive in utilizing the various opportunities of engagement with European Commission actors, as well as responding to requests for information or invitations for participation in events (e.g. AgrilInnovation, France, June 2019).

1.1.10.1. Direct engagement with DG Agri and other DGs

Members of Units of DG Agri and DG ENV of particular relevance to UNISECO have signed up to the EU-level MAP, participated in workshops and engaged in exchanges of project documents and discussions, and facilitated wider involvement of DG Agri and DG ENV in seminars and other project events. UNISECO attended the Coordinator’s Day organised by the European Commission Research Executive Agency in June 2018, presented the project in a session of the project cluster “Bioeconomy policy and Rural Innovation”, and has organised exchanges with other relevant H2020 projects (see Section 1.3.5).

A participatory scenario development workshop with the EU level MAP was organised on 1st March 2019. Thirteen stakeholders attended the workshop including representatives of DG Agri and DG ENV, the European Network for Rural Development, the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development, farmer and landowner organisations, the FAO, and NGOs. The objectives of the first workshop in the scenario development process was to: i) develop a shared understanding of the scenario development purpose and process to be carried out in the UNISECO project; ii) create understanding of which analyses are possible with the models that will be used in UNISECO; and , iii) collect input from stakeholders on what should be explored in the scenarios.

On 21st January 2019 a joint seminar of the UNISECO and LIFT projects took place at DG Agri, Brussels, Belgium, to introduce both projects to the relevant Units of DG Agri and DG ENV, and to facilitate science-policy interaction. The meeting was co-organised by DG Agri, REA and the two projects, and was attended by representatives of different units at DG Agri and DG ENV. Following

brief introductions of both projects discussions focussed on issues in relation to the farming typologies developed in the projects, tools and indicators to analyse sustainability at farm and territorial levels, as well as data available from the European Commission such as the European FADN data.

In addition, UNISECO collaborates with European Network for Rural Development and the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development which is coordinated by DG Agri.

1.1.10.2. Engagement with the European Network for Rural Development and the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development

Members of European Network for Rural Development and the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development have signed up to the EU-level MAP, participate in workshops and other UNISECO events, and to contribute to further dissemination and awareness raising of project events and results (Figure 20). The engagement of UNISECO with the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development builds on successful impact generation in previous projects such as the FP7 project ENVIEVAL. In that case, a new Interactive Decision Tool for the selection of evaluation approaches, and guidelines published by the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development for the assessment of RDP achievements and impacts, built on the logic model approach developed by the ENVIEVAL project.

UNISECO also participated in the ENRD Seminar on 'Bioeconomy: Seizing the opportunities for rural Europe' which included discussions on carbon sinks in rural areas, key barriers to scaling up rural bioeconomy initiatives and examples of policy coherence enabling rural bioenergy production.

Figure 20. ENRD Contact Point tweet about a UNISECO workshop.

1.1.10.3. UNISECO engagement with EIP-Agri Service Point and use of their tools

During the First Reporting Period the EIP-Agri Service Point has included UNISECO in the multi-actor projects database. This is a list of projects in which end users and multipliers of research results such as farmers and farmers groups, advisers, enterprises and others, are cooperating closely throughout the time of their research projects (Figure 21). The information can be found at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects>.

Figure 21. UNISECO in the EIP-Agri multi-actor project database.

In addition, Pille Koorberg, a team member and rural development expert of the EIP-Agri Service Point, is a member of the UNISECO Project Advisory Group (<https://uniseco-project.eu/project-advisory-group>). Their involvement in the Project Advisory Group, and the regular interactions between it and the project partners, ensures a regular screening and identification of possible engagement opportunities with EIP-Agri. Close links with EIP-Agri Operational Groups and local contact points in the partner countries are also maintained.

UNISECO was also invited to the Agri-Innovation Summit 2019 (Lisieux, France) organised by the EIP-Agri Service Point in June 2019 (Figure 22). The presentation and participation of UNISECO at the summit enabled the dissemination of results and networking with a wide range of rural, agricultural and environmental stakeholder and policy-makers and resulted in follow-up activities exploring co-operation with other multi-actor projects such as DiverIMPACTS.

Figure 22. UNISECO poster at the Agri-Innovation Summit 2019.

1.1.10.4. UNISECO on CORDIS Twitter

The EU Research Results Twitter account referred to the UNISECO project (Figure 23), explaining that the project team is aiming at understanding and improving the sustainability of agro-ecological farming systems.

Figure 23. Reference to the UNISECO project on the CORDIS Twitter account.

1.2. Dissemination Materials and Publications

Materials were produced during the first 18 months of the project to support its visibility. These materials include a project leaflet (See Appendix 4.18) which was prepared and published in English. A template was also created for the partners to translate the leaflet into national languages, with versions now available in German, Hungarian and Italian (<https://uniseco-project.eu/resources>; Appendix 4.18). A roll-up poster (See Appendix 4.19) about the project was also designed and printed for use at relevant events. Videos have been recorded for the UNISECO project websites and other channels to promote the project and its work.

1.2.1. Project leaflet

The project leaflet (Figure 24) was created at the beginning of the project. A template for collecting partner language translations was also developed. The project leaflet is available in English, German, Hungarian and Italian languages from the project website Resources section. <https://uniseco-project.eu/news/3/>.

The project flyer is used across various face-to-face communication and dissemination activities including conferences, workshops, meetings, interviews and consultations. Example of the events at which the project leaflet was used are listed in Appendix 4.6.

Figure 24. Front page of the UNISECO project leaflet.

1.2.2. UNISECO roll-up poster

The project roll-up poster got ready for the 2nd project meeting in Venice, Italy. The project roll-up is available in several languages and used at face-to-face communication and dissemination activities including conferences, workshops, project meetings and stakeholder consultations (Figure 25 and Figure 33).

Figure 25. The roll-up poster used as a backdrop at events such as the stakeholder workshop in Helsinki, Finland, May 2019.

1.2.3. Publications and communication in mass media

This deliverable reports on communication, dissemination and impact of project activities during the first 18 months of the project, 1st April 2018 to 31st October 2019, was prepared using the reporting by project partners in their quarterly ‘COMMDIS reports’ (one per partner, per quarter) and summarising the results from webpage and social media analytical tools.

Several hundred different activities were carried out by 18 partners during the first 18 months. The estimated number of people reached per action varied from 1 stakeholder to 1.1 million possible listeners of a national radio broadcast. Approximately 2 million people from different audiences were reached. Not all participants at every event can be counted. Attempts have been made to limit the reporting to the number of people with whom there was evidence of engagement, or direct contact. Audiences of mass media channels are estimated using the statistics provided by the relevant publication or broadcaster. Partner SLU reached the largest audience with 3 articles in the popular press (e.g. Figure 26) which reached between 100,000 to 350,000 readers and a science report in a national radio broadcast (1.1 million).

Figure 26. An example of one of the articles in the popular press in Sweden.

The activities carried out by project partners covers a broad range of forms and media. These included presentations, articles on partner websites, social media, newspapers, radio, national and international events, workshops, newsletters, press releases, videos, and e-mails. The most frequent activities were oral presentations, discussions, workshops, sessions and other different events, press articles, and poster presentations. The most popular form of activity used by most of the partners was an oral or other type of presentation, as shown in the word cloud of the types of communication and dissemination activities (Figure 27).

All of the project’s target audiences were reached: stakeholders, scientists, farmers, researchers, national and international institutions, governments, conference participants, and the general public.

Figure 27. Word cloud of communication and dissemination activities during the first 18 months of the UNISECO project.

1.3. External peer-to-peer exchange

All project partners presented the UNISECO to peer groups, whether science, policy or practice. The information communicated covered project objectives, activities and results. The principal channels for communicating were websites, social media and newsletters, and through events, conferences and workshops. They also included international and national conferences, workshops, exhibitions and panels (e.g. Figure 28).

Figure 28. UNISECO partners (GAN) presenting the project in the conference CONAMA 2018.

1.3.1. Organisation of conference sessions

The UNISECO project team organised two oral sessions and poster session at the Annual meeting of the Association of American Geographers (AAG) meeting in Washington DC, USA, in April 2019 (Figures 29 and 30). These sessions included invited contributions from the H2020 LIFT and SUFISA projects.

Figure 29. UNISECO organised session at the Association of American Geographers (AAG) meeting in Washington DC, USA, in April 2019 on “Agroecological Transitions in a Transatlantic Context”.

Figure 30. Photographs of the oral and poster sessions organised by UNISECO at the Association of American Geographers (AAG) meeting in Washington DC, USA, in April 2019.

At the 8th AIEAA Conference “Tomorrow’s Food: Diet transition and its implications on health and the environment” the UNISECO project team, with teams from the H2020 projects CONSOLE and CONTRACT2.0, organised a session on “Emerging issues and instruments in public goods provision from agriculture”. The session also included a presentation from the H2020 LIFT project.

1.3.2. Organisation of workshops

During First Reporting Period, UNISECO project partners organised 15 workshops. These included workshops in the case studies with the members of the case study MAPs and (in addition to the

above highlighted conference sessions), and at international conferences such as the Agroecology Europe Forum 2019. These workshops brought together different types of stakeholders from the European Commission and its agencies, local authorities, farmers, the public sector and NGOs). In total, approximately 200 people from target audiences participated in such workshops. Photographs of such project workshops are shown in Figure 31.

The workshops covered a range of different themes of technical or thematic relevance to the project, usually based on the work in the national case studies.

Figure 31. Photographs of examples of project workshops held by project partners.

1.3.3. Participation at conferences and workshops

During the First Reporting Period, UNISECO project partners participated in 15 international and national conferences (Appendix 4.8) and 6 national and international workshops (Appendix 4.9). Target audiences included members of the European Parliament, scientists, nature conservation bodies, NGOs. There was also participation in 15 events other than conferences or workshops (Appendix 4.10), and the events of 5 other projects (Appendix 4.12) and 4 European Commission /European Union events (Appendixes 4.14).

The project held meetings with other stakeholders or contributed to consultations on public policy, (Appendix 4.15). These forms of communication created opportunities to present the project to a wider audience, distribute project materials, and to contribute to mechanisms of public policy.

The topics or themes covered in these events were analysed for the production of a word cloud (Figure 32) which gives an indication of the prominence of reference to the European Commission, DGs Agri and ENV, and the H2020 LIFT project, and thus the contribution of those bodies to the events. Examples of the use of the visual identify of the UNISECO project, and displays which it supports, to promote the project are illustrated in Figure 33.

Figure 32. Word cloud of themes of events during the first 18 months of the UNISECO project.

Figure 33. Word cloud of themes of events during the first 18 months of the UNISECO project.

1.3.4. Collaborating with fellow project LIFT financed under same topic

Contacts with the H2020 LIFT project ('Low-Input Farming and Territories - Integrating knowledge for improving ecosystem-based farming') consortium have been well established through the First Reporting Period. Dr Laure Latruffe, LIFT Project Coordinator (INRA, Rennes, France), participated in the UNISECO kick-off meeting at which opportunities of shared activities were discussed.

Similar engagement took place with the participation of Gerald Schwarz, UNISECO Project Coordinator (Thünen Institute, Germany), at the kick-off meeting of the H2020 LIFT project. A representative of the LIFT project also attended the 3rd full partner meeting of UNISECO, in Helsinki, Finland, and UNISECO will continue to attend LIFT meetings, when invited.

Synergies have been being sought between the two projects through dissemination actions (see Section 1.3.1), the exchange of materials (e.g. on typologies developed in both projects), cross referencing in project newsletters, establishing links between websites and social media channels. The teams working on relevant topics will work to ensure coherent and mutually complimentary communications whenever appropriate (e.g. farming typologies). UNISECO devotes a standing column in its 6 monthly newsletters devoted to highlights of links with the LIFT project.

Meetings have also taken place between the LIFT and UNISECO projects at national levels, such as where both projects have case studies in the same country. The aim of the meetings in France, Greece, Hungary Italy and the UK have been to discuss the approaches in the project and the case studies to identify possible synergies that can be utilised.

1.3.5. Collaborating with other projects

In the First Reporting Period, UNISECO has established close ties with other relevant initiatives under EU-funded, international or national programmes, helping to raise awareness and impacts amongst the target audience groups. Partners identified opportunities to participate in each other's events and the organisation of shared events. With this as an aim, close links have been established at both central and local project levels.

At a project level, while attending the project Coordinators' Day, organised by the European Commission Research Executive Agency, exchanges were made with other relevant H2020 projects such as LANDSUPPORT and ECOSTACK.

UNISECO makes use of, and integrates with, relevant activities of projects and events to add value, avoid duplication of effort and dilution of impact on policy advisors, and maximise combined impacts. Contacts with other European Union level research consortia and teams working on agroecological systems or relevant topics have been established to ensure coherent and complimentary communications. Synergies are sought in dissemination actions, exchange of materials, establishing links between websites and co-operation to increase efficiency of deliverables.

Joint dissemination activities with other H2020 projects included conference sessions and workshops with the COFARM, CONSOLE, CONTRACT2.0, FARMDEMO, LIFT, SIMRA and SUFISA projects. With PROVIDE, UNISECO contributed to its final conference (<https://uniseco-project.eu/news/4/uniseco-presented-at-provide-regional-final-conference-in-italy>) (Figure 34). Collaborations have also been through contributions to international events such as FFA 2019, FEAL Conference, MAES Stakeholder workshop, CARE-T-FARMS event, and the Best of Portugal (Figure 35).

Figure 34. UNISECO presented at the H2020 PROVIDE project regional conference.

Figure 35. Photographs of examples of networking events to which UNISECO has contributed in the First Reporting Period.

Examples of related activities at national levels are: i) the MEDIATE project, Germany, using participatory approaches to develop targeted schemes for increasing agrobiodiversity; ii) Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2016-21; and use of its Centre for Sustainable Cropping research platform (Balruddery farm, James Hutton Institute, Dundee, United Kingdom).

2. IMPACT EVALUATION: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS RELATED TO COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

There are 3 key performance indicators related to communication and dissemination activities. These are listed in Table 2 together with the original target for the full 36 month period of the project, and the total achieved in the First Reporting Period.

Table 2. Key performance indicators: Targets and total achieved in the First Reporting Period.

	Cumulative Target (full project period)	Total Achieved
KPI 07 Number of website hits	800	6,043
KPI 08 Twitter followers	200	300
KPI 09 Subscribe to newsletter	100	130

The number of communication and dissemination activities under taken for each of the categories of activity is shown in Table 3 together with a cross-reference to the relevant appendix in which more information is provided.

Table 3. The number of communication and dissemination activities linked to the project by category.

Category	Number of and Communication Dissemination Activities	Relevant Appendix
Organisation of Conference Sessions	3	4.1
Organisation of Workshops	15	4.2
Press releases	1	4.3
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications (popular articles)	4	4.4
Training	1	4.5
News items on project website	45	4.6
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	1	4.7
Participation in Conferences	15	4.8
Participation in Workshops	6	4.9
Participation in Events other than a Conference or a Workshop	15	4.10
Videos and Films	5	4.11
Participation in activities organized jointly with other European Union projects	5	4.12

Category	Number of and Communication Dissemination Activities	Relevant Appendix
Other: Relating to the UNISECO Newsletter	12	4.13
Other: Events with the European Commission/ European Union	4	4.14
Other: Meetings and consultations	11	4.15
Other: on-line repositories - Researchgate followers, reads	29,175	
Social Media: LI posts, tweets	147 tweet + 77 LinkedIn post	4.17
Project flyer/ leaflet	450	4.18

Estimated of the number of people reached through the communication and dissemination activities are provided in Table 4. The estimated number of members of the general public reached is based upon the circulation figures for the media outlets (e.g. radio broadcasts, newspapers).

Table 4. The estimated number of people reached through the communication and dissemination and activities by category.

Category	Estimated Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1,360
Industry	891
Civil Society	1,778
General Public	1,340,404
Policy Makers	920
Media	7
Investors	-
Customers	5
Other	15,579

3. REFERENCES

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4. APPENDICES

4.1. Organisation of Conference Sessions

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P01 TI	Annual Meeting AAG 2019. Organisation of three sessions: "Agroecological transitions in a transatlantic context (1): concepts, typologies, barriers, drivers and sustainability performance" "Agroecological transitions in a transatlantic context (2): concepts, typologies, barriers, drivers and sustainability performance" "Agroecological transitions in a transatlantic context (3): concepts, typologies, barriers, drivers and sustainability performance";	6.4.2019	Gerald Schwarz / Co-organisers: Inge Aalders (HUT), Katalin Balazs (GEO), Francesco Vanni (CREA); 3 Oral presentations and 3 poster presentations on UNISECO Presenters: Inge Aalders (HUT), Katalin Balazs (GEO), Kate Irvine (HUT, Alexandra Smyrniotopoulou (AUA), Gerald Schwarz, Francesco Vanni (CREA) LIFT H2020 project SUFISA H2020 project	Scientists	25	Posters, PPT slides
P02 CRE A	8th AIEAA Conference, Organised Session: "Emerging issues and instruments in public goods provision from agriculture"/ EU market and policy incentives supporting the transitions towards agro-ecological farming systems	14.6.2019	Francesco Vanni, Andrea Povellato/ CONSOLE project CONTRACT 2.0 project LIFT project	Scientists	15	PPT slides

4.2. Organisation of Workshops

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P13 SLU, P12 LUKE	First Stakeholder Workshop on the participatory scenario development in Task 4.3 and the spatially explicit online tool (SESSIT) in Task 6.1	01.3.2019	Elin Rööös, Andreas Mayer (BOKU), Janne Helin (LUKE), Jan Landert (FiBL, Andrea Povellato (CREA)	EU stakeholders	10	
P03 AUA	Workshop organised with case study MAP members for the Social Network Analysis in Task 5.2 in the Greek case study	30.7.2019	Alexandra Smyrniotopoulou and George Vlahos	Farmers, advisors, fruit processors, actor of public sector	7	
P12 LUKE	Stakeholder workshop/ Presentation and feedback session on the SESSIT	8.5.2019	Janne Helin	EU stakeholders	15	
P01 TI	Workshop organised with case study MAP members for the Social Network Analysis in Task 5.2 in the German case study	9.9.2019	Gerald Schwarz Johannes Carolus	Stakeholder	8	PPT slides, discussion notes, social network maps
P03 AUA	2nd Agroecology Europe Forum/ Workshop 4: Research aspects - Bringing it all together	26-28.09.2019	UNISECO members (Gerald Schwarz, Katalin Balazs, George Vlahos and Alexandra Smyrniotopoulou) and other external researchers	Academics, researchers, NGO members, etc.	20	
P05 HUT	UNISECO Scottish Case Study workshop	22.04.2019	David Miller, Kate Irvine, Inge Aalders, Pete Smith (UNIABDN), Fabrizio Albanito (UNIABDN)	Farmers	8	
P05 HUT	Food, farming and Countryside Workshop - / 'A Celebration of Land and Sea'	20.03.2019	David Miller, Inge Aalders	Policy makers, NGOs, farmers, scientists	22	
P05 HUT	Meeting with local actors/ Food, farming and Countryside Workshop	29.04.2019	David Miller	Policy makers, NGOs, farmers, scientists	18	
P07 ISARA	SNA workshop + SES analysis + exchanges with a part of the French team of H2020 LIFT (Auvergne)	30.09.2019	Audrey Vincent Philippe Fleury	Local stakeholders:	9	
P09 BEF LT	Workshop for stakeholders/ How to maintain and encourage extensive management (grazing) of grassland habitats and	30.09.2019	Gražvydas Jegelevičius, Elvyra Mikšytė, Audronė Alijošiūtė-Paulauskienė, Eglė Ruškutė	Local stakeholders	16	

	how to become (or remain) competitive in the market without intensifying the farming practice.					
P10 FIBL	First local MAP workshop	2.4.2019	Rebekka Frick Jan Landert Bettina Scharrer (University of Bern)	Farmer, Advisors, Administration, Industry	24	
P10 FIBL	Workshop in Task 3.2 with farmers.	15.10.2019	Rebekka Frick Jan Landert	Farmers, Advisors	8	
P12 LUKE	UNISECO farm workshop	31.10.2019	Kaija Vähäsöyrinki /Jarkko Pyysiäinen	Lokal stakeholders	10	
P15 WWF	Workshop organised with case study MAP members for the Social Network Analysis in Task 5.2 in the Romanian case study	11.08.2019	Mihaela Fratila	Local stakeholders: representatives of Agricultural institutions, farmers and Producers, representatives of Agroturism and Ecoturism Association, Environmental NGOÖs	21	
P02 CREA	Workshop organised with case study MAP members for the Social Network Analysis in Task 5.2 in the Italian case study	16.07.2019	Francesco Vanni Orianan Gava Andrea Povellato	Farmers, advisors, authorities, environmental NGOs, value chain, scientists	10	PPT slides, discussion notes, Net maps

4.3. Press Releases

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P07 ISARA	Press release of the presentation/ "la revue du réseau rural français, N°13, 2018, p. 18.	1st trimester 2018		General public		

4.4. Non-scientific and Non-peer-reviewed Publications (popular articles)

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P13 SLU	Interview for article in the popular press/ "SLU looking for farmers for a transition of more plant-based farming	18.02.2019	Elin Rööös and Adam Arnesson (case study MAP member)	Farmers, the public	180 000 readers every week	
P13 SLU	Interview for article in the popular press/ "The organic farmer Adam is investing in peas instead of more	4.03.2019	Elin Rööös and Adam Arnesson (case study MAP	Public	The newspaper has 100 000	

	animals - now his farm becomes part of an EU project"		member)		readers	
P13 SLU	Interview for article in the popular press/ "Farmer looking for seeds - the way for a meat producer to be more climate smart"	24.03.2019	Elin Rööös and Adam Arnesson (case study MAP member)	Public	The newspaper has 350 000 readers	
P12 LUKE	Article in popular press Laitossuunnittelu valmistumassa – Valion ja Gasumin biokaasulaitos odottaa valtion tukilinjauksia	27.9.2019	Jarkko Pyysiäinen	Public	Not known	

4.5. Training

UNISECO training for on-farm sustainability assessments

Three Decision Support Tools COMPAS, Cool Farm and SMART will be applied to assess the economic, environmental and social performance of agro-ecological and conventional farms in the UNISECO case studies.

The UNISECO project partners were trained on the use of the three decision support tools. The training was organised by the FiBL project partner in preparation for the UNISECO case studies, taking place from the 18th to 23rd February 2019 at the Organic Research Centre in Newbury, United Kingdom. The training included 11 farm visits to gain experience in the practical application of the SMART tool (Figure 36).

The UNISECO consortium thanks the Organic Research Centre for hosting the training, the Cool Farm Alliance for the demonstration of the Cool Farm Tool and the farmers for their hospitality and time for the interesting and helpful farm visits.

<https://uniseco-project.eu/news/15/>

Figure 36. Training in Decision Support Tools, meeting with farmers, Newbury, United Kingdom.

4.6. News Items on Project Website

A total of 45 news items were published on the project website. For details of news items on the UNISECO project see <https://uniseco-project.eu/news-and-events>.

4.7. Communication Campaign

The communications of project activities and findings are being directed through a range of media channels, including radio and television

Partnr	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P13 SLU	National radio - science reporting/ "More cultivation for less meat"	28.02.2019	Elin Rööös/ Jan Bengtsson	Public	This radio channels has 1.1 million daily listeners	

4.8. Participation in Conferences

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P01 TI	GfÖ conference: 48th Annual Meeting of the Ecological Society of Germany, Austria and Switzerland/ Poster presentation	11.09.2018	Gerald Schwarz	Scientists	30	Poster
P01 TI	COFARM Final Conference: Introduction to the UNISECO project –cooperation and co-learning in agro-ecological transitions/ Oral presentation	24.4.2019	Gerald Schwarz	NGOs, Farm Associations, Researchers in Agriculture	50	PPT slides
P08 BEF LV	Scientific conference: „Zemes apsaimniekošana atbilstoši bioloģiskās lauksaimniecības principiem – ilgtspējīgs ieguldījums Latvijas nākotnē”	06.02.2019	Andis Zilāns			PPT slides
P17 ELO	COFARM Final Conference	24.04.2019	Conference organisers: Alice Budniok, Branwen Miles,	NGOs, Farm Associations, Researchers in Agriculture	50	Brochures
P01 TI	8th AIEAA Conference/ Tomorrow's Food: Diet transition and its implications on health and the environment	14.6.2019	Gerald Schwarz	Scientists	15	PPT slides
P08 BEF LV	8th Conference of the Italian Association of Agricultural and Applied Economics/Presentation prepared	14.06.2019	Andis Zilāns	Scientists	15	PPT slides
P11 GEO	Mission possible? International conference on agricultural biodiversity	23.05.2019	GEO	conference audience, stakeholders from the agriculture and input suppliers	100	3 posters+ 30 project leaflets

				industry, FAO		
P17 ELO	Farm Demo Conference	21.05.2019	Lindsey Chubb	Farmers, Farm Associations, EU/national Policy officers	200+	Brochures, Activity Report
P17 ELO	FEAL Conference	06.05.2019	ELO Projects Team	ELO Members, Policy officers, EESC Members and people interested in multifunctional farming	50	
P01 TI	Ecosystem Services Partnership 10th World Conference/ Oral presentation	21 to 25 October 2019	Johannes Carolus/an Landert, Fabrizio Albanito, Gerald Schwarz, Adrian Muller, Pete Smith, Jörn Sanders, Christian Schader	Scientists	20	PPT slides
P01 TI	RBP Network Conference/ Oral presentation	16 to 17.9.2019	Gerald Schwarz	Scientists, ministries, DG Env	40	PPT slides
P14 GAN	Conference within the Summer Courses of the UPV (University of the Basque Country)/ Oral communication to local and regional stakeholder	27.09.2019	Uxue Iragui Yoldi	Local and regional stakeholders	5	
P14 GAN	Conference of INTIA (regional public company)/ Explotaciones agrarias, sistemas agroalimentarios y sostenibilidad (Farms, agri-food systems and sustainability)	26.09.2019	Paola Eguinoa Ancho (INTIA)	Local and regional stakeholders	100	PPT presentation
BEF-LT	Participation in a conference, oral contact exchange/ Experience of sustainable farming in the context of climate change	01.08.2019	Grazvydas Jegelevicius, Audrone Alijosiute-Paulauskiene	Local stakeholders	100	

4.9. Participation in Workshops

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P17 ELO	Maes Stakeholder Workshop	17 to 18.06.2019	Lindsey Chubb	Policy advisors, biodiversity specialists	30	Brochures
P11 GEO	International workshop: nature friendly farming - Birdlife, EEB, NABU	9.09.2019	Katalin Balazs	EU parliament members, scientists, nature	20	20 project leaflets

				conservation stakeholders, EU DG ENV		
P14 GAN	Workshop of WWF and SEOBirdLife on the new CAP	29.10.2019	Carlos Astrain Mass	National stakeholders	20-30	
P15 WWF	EIP-AGRI workshop "Small is smart - Innovative solutions for small agricultural and forestry holdings"	29 to 30.10.2019	Mara Cazacu	Researchers, farm advisors/consultants & contractors, farmers, DG Agri reps, ministry reps	50	booklet produced and distributed by EIP-AGRI, containing a factsheet on the project
PO2 CREA	Workshop on agroecology organised by the Central Italy Association for Agroecology	12.11.2019	Francesco Galioto	National public	40	
PO2 CREA	Workshop on Organic Olive Oil	20.06.2019	Francesco Vanni, Letizia Rossignonolo	Stakeholders, local farmers, consultants, regional officers	40	Notes

4.10. Participation in Events other than a Conference or a Workshop

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P17 ELO	Tree of the Year	19.03.2019	Daniel Monteleone	European Landowners		Brochures
P17 ELO	Forum for the Future of Agriculture (FFA)	08.04.2019	ELO Projects Team	MEPs, NGOs, DGs	1500	50 Brochures and incorporation of interactive board
P17 ELO	Best of Portugal	04 to 05.05.2019	ELO Projects Team	Confederation of Portuguese Farmers	40,000	
P17 ELO	25/06/2019	25.06.2019	ELO Projects Team	Farmers, NGOs	60	Brochures, Activity Report
PO5 HUT	Royal Highland Show/ Farmer and actor business exhibition	20 to 23.06.2019	David Miller	Farmers, elected representatives, policy officers, public agencies, public (including children)	100	A4 copies of poster, project flier, stakeholder information sheets

PO5 HUT	Visit by Royal Town Planning Institute, Grampian Chapter	8.10.2019	David Miller/ C Wang, G Donaldson-Selby	Planners in local authority	5	A4 copies of poster, project flyer
PO5 HUT	Lecture on GIS and Landscape scale conservation	8.01.2019	David Miller/ Ian Brown, Marie Castellazzi	Undergraduate students (Honours)	12	Powerpoint slides, link to project flier
P11 GEO	Soil conservation farming demonstration farm field day	19.09.2019	GEO	farmer, advisor	2	2 printed flyers in HU language
P18 BIONIST	Roundtable discussion with Czech case study farmers/ Presentation of UNISECO, Czech Case Study and DTS, data collection process presentation	18.6.2019	Andrea Hrabalová	Farmers in OF with milk in Vysočina Region	5	PP presentation, Flyer in CZ
P18 BIONIST	Colloquium of research in OF - overall presentation of UNISECO project	15.10.2019	Andrea Hrabalová	representatives of research organizations and universities	40	Project flyer and information about the case study in CZ
P06 UNIABDN	University seminar/ Understanding and improving the sustainability of agro-ecological farming in Scotland	24.10.2019	Fabrizio Albanito	Scholars and students	35	
P07 ISARA	A 3 days training session with students dedicated to SES approach in collective work	14 to 17.09.19	Audrey Vincent Philippe Fleury,	students	28	operational SES template, and documents (*7)
P13 SLU	Presentation at Centre for Business and Policy Studies, an independent think tank	8.10.2018	Elin Rööös	Public	Approximately 60 people attending, the seminar was also sent on Swedish television	
P13 SLU	Presentation for the Swedish Church, large land owner	9.10.2018	Elin Rööös	Employees at the Swedish Church working with land management	60	
P18 BIOINST	Roundtable discussion with Czech case study farmer	18.6.2019	Andrea Hrabalová	Farmers in OF with milk in Vysočina Region	5	PP presentation, Flyer in CZ

4.11. Videos and Films

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P11 GEO	Video published on project website with GD project officer	Oct 2018	GEO/HUT	Website visitors	843	

P11 GEO	Video with PAG member Peter Goddard	Nov 2018 - video recorded Febr 2019 - published with consent	GEO/HUT	youtube visitors	19	
P11 GEO	Video with Andrea Furlan EC DG AGRI	Nov 2018 - video recorded Febr 2019 - published with consent	GEO/HUT	youtube visitors	20	
P11 GEO	Video with Hilde Bjorkhaug PAG member	Nov 2018 - video recorded Febr 2019 - published with consent	GEO/HUT	youtube visitors	17	
P07 ISARA	Website and subtitle videos in French / translation for UNISECO Website and main actors of EU Commission	31.01.2019	Emmanuel GuisePELLI			

4.12. Participation in Activities with Other European Union Projects (see also Appendix 4.1)

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P01 TI	LIFT Project kick-off Meeting / Oral presentation	27.06.2018	Gerald Schwarz	Scientists, DG Agri Policy Officer	40	
P01 TI	UNISECO and CONSOLE DE teams meeting	10.09.2019	Gerald Schwarz, Johannes Carolus, Tania Runge (CONSOLE)	Researchers	3	Project flyer
P02 CREA	H2020 PROVIDE project/ BENI PUBBLICI, AGRICOLTURA E FORESTE: i risultati del progetto PROVIDE e le implicazioni per la PAC post 2020	11.07.2018	Andrea Povellato	Regional officers, consultants, scientists	30	
P07 ISARA	FR EIP (European Innovation Partnerships) consulting committee	06.06.2018	Philippe Fleury	Regional and national officers, local and regional stakeholders	50	
P11 GEO	UNISECO-LIFT HU teams meeting	11.10.2018	GEO/ UNISECO-LIFT HU team	researchers	2	2 project flyers
P15 WWF	CAP Meeting WWF RO; Defining WWF's action on the CAP as a priority element in the WWF initiative on the agricultural sector and an	18.12.2018	Members of Policy Team in Romania	WWF Policy team	12	

	update of activities with focus on agriculture (UNISECO We have reviewed the information collected from the field for WP 5, interviews with stakeholders to identify innovative measures for Market and Policy Incentives Supporting AEFS.					
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4.13. Other: Relating to the UNISECO Newsletter

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P03 AUA	Information email about UNISECO and UNISECO flyer sent to AUA team professional contacts encouraging them to subscribe to UNISECO Newsletter.	Dec 2018		academics, NGO members, public officers	40	Project flyer
P09 BEF LT	Post about first published newsletter	19.12.2018		BEF LT FB followers	700	
P09 BEF LT	Post about first published newsletter	19.12.2018		BEF LT LinkedIn followers	50	
P09 BEF LT	Post encouraging to subscribe to UNISECO's newsletter	15.11.2018		BEF LT FB followers	400	
P09 BEF LT	Text about first published newsletter	19.12.2018		Website visitors		
P09 BEF LT	Text encouraging to subscribe to UNISECO's newsletter	15.11.2018		Website visitors		
P11 GAN	Information e-mail with project flyer in Spanish and with links to encourage local and national stakeholders to subscribe to UNISECO Newsletter and to follow the project in Twitter and LinkedIn	December 2018		Local stakeholders involved in case study selection, and national stakeholders involved in interviews about agro-ecological market and policy incentives in Spain	8	Project flyer
P03 AUA	Invitation email for SNA workshop along with info about UNISECO and UNISECO flyer sent to candidate local MAP members encouraging them to visit website and subscribe to UNISECO Newsletter.	mid July 2019		farmers, advisors, fruit processors, actor of public sector	8	Project flyer
P08 BEF LV	Information about UNISECO 2nd newsletter project in organisations website	10.07.2019		Website visitors		
P08 BEF LV	Information about UNISECO 2nd newsletter project in organisations website LV	10.07.2019		Website visitors		

P09 BEF LT	Article about 2nd newsletter	15.07.2019		Bef.It website visitors		
P14 GAN	Update on UNISECO and presentation of the case study in the 14th internal newsletter of GAN	02.07.2019	Uxue Iragui Yoldi	GAN staff	100	Information on the project and the case study of Spain
P01 TI	Invitation email for SNA workshop along with info about UNISECO and UNISECO flyer sent to candidate local MAP members encouraging them to visit website and subscribe to UNISECO Newsletter.	19.08.2019		Farmers, advisors, processors, local authorities and administrations	12	Project flyer

4.14. Other: Events Organised by European Commission/European Union

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P01 TI	H2020 Coordinator's Day/ Oral presentation	15.06.2018	Gerald Schwarz/ UNISECO team	DG Agri, REA, EIP-Agri, scientists	30	PPT Slides
P01 TI	Seminar at DG Agri/ Oral presentation	21.01.2019	Gerald Schwarz/ Inge Aalders (separate presentation), Adrian Müller (separate presentation), Elin Rööös and Andrea Povellato	DG Agri, DG ENV, REA	14	PPT Slides
P01 TI	EIP-Agri: Agri Innovation summit 2019/ Poster presentation	25 to 26.6.2019	Gerald Schwarz	DG Agri, REA, EIP-Agri, stakeholders, scientists	80	Poster

4.15. Other: Meetings and Consultations

Partner	Event/ Title of Activity	Date	Author (presenter)/ Others Involved	Type of Audience Reached	Estimated Number of People Reached	Dissemination Material Distributed
P05 HUT	Response to Public Consultation from Scottish Government National Council of Rural Advisers 'A Rural Conversation: Together We Can, Together We Will'	24.07. 2018	D Miller/ James Hutton Institute staff	Policy officers, Scottish Government		
P05 HUT	Response to Public Consultation from Scottish Government on Support for Agriculture and the Rural Economy - Post Brexit Transition	15.08.2018	D Miller/ James Hutton Institute staff	Policy officers, Scottish Government		
P15	Meeting Leuphana university and Southern	27.09.2018	Mihaela Fratila	academic, representativ	20	

WWF	Transylvanian Research/ Oral presentation			es of local community		
P18 BIOINST	regular meeting of members the Commission for the implementation of the Action Plan for the OF Development in the Czech Republic by 2020	24.10.2018	Andrea Hrabalová	key stakeholders in the OF sector	20	CZ
P14 GAN	Overall presentation of UNISECO in the Government of Navarra	16.04.2019	Uxue Iragui Yoldi	Government of Navarra. Bureau for the Promotion of Organic Agriculture and Cross- Sectoral Actions in the Agricultural Sector	2	Project flyer and information on the case study of Spain
P14 GAN	Meeting for coordination activities of the Dehesa/Montado with respect to the CAP payments and HNVF	26 to 27.03.2019	Uxue Iragui Yoldi	WWF Spain, IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature), Transhumanc e and Nature	7	
P01 TI	Meeting of the thematic group of agroecology of the Federal Ministry of food and Agriculture and the Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development	28.03.2019	Gerald Schwarz	Ministry staff	10	PPT slides
P01 TI	Meeting of the Agricultural Committee of NABU Lower Saxony	28/10/2019	Gerald Schwarz Johannes Carolus	Environmenta l NGOs and organic farmers	12	PPT slides
P05 HUT	Meeting with local actors. Tour of cooperatives, organised by Scottish Agricultural Organisation Society	20.08.2019	D Miller	Policy makers, NGOs, farmers, scientists	5	Project flier, stakeholder information sheets
P05 HUT	Meeting with DG Agri/ Kick- off meeting of H2020 SHERPA project	21.10.2019	D Miller and G. Schwarz	DG Agri policy liaison	1	
P17 ELO	BIOPLAT-EU 1st Progress Meeting	08 to 09.05.2019	Lindsey Chubb	Agricultural Experts & Researchers	20	ELO Activity Report
P17 ELO	Console H2020 Project Meeting	30 to 1.10.2019	Alice Budniok and Branwen Miles	Project Consortium	30	

4.16. Website News Items, Social Media Posts Database

For the details of news items on the UNISECO project see the project website. The lists of website items and social media posts are stored in a social media database.

4.17. Project Newsletters

Copies of the UNISECO project newsletters are available through the following links:

- Newsletter 1 - December 2018: <http://uniseco-project.eu/newsletter/issue/1/uniseco-newsletter-december-2018>
- Newsletter 2 – July 2019: https://uniseco-project.eu/assets/content/resources/03-newsletters/uniseco-newsletter-Nr02-vFINAL.pdf?utm_campaign=UNISECONL&utm_source=NL201907&utm_medium=e-mail

4.18. Project Flyer/Leaflet

A trifold leaflet has been produced for the UNISECO project, in 4 of the languages of project partners. It has been distributed at more than 10 events (marked in the event tables), and made available at numerous others. It was also posted on national websites and distributed via email to the project target audiences. Approximately 450 people were reached with the project flyer/leaflet.

Examples follow of the leaflet in English, German, Hungarian and Italian languages.

English language version of the UNISECO leaflet, side 1 -

Countries in which participatory case studies will be carried out to test the UNISECO methodological toolkit to assess the environmental, economic and social impacts of innovative strategies and incentives for agro-ecological approaches:

COORDINATED BY

CONTACT

Dr Gerald Schwarz
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 Phone: +49 531 596 5140
 Thünen Institute
 Bundesallee 63 38116 Braunschweig
 GERMANY

GET INVOLVED

- 📍 Participate in national workshops
- 📍 Participate in the case studies
- 📍 Contribute to our virtual Multi-Actor Platform online community (MAP-NEF)

FOLLOW US

UNISECO website & Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub
<https://uniseco-project.eu>

Sign up for our regular newsletter, and follow us on social media!

- 🐦 UNISECO Project
- 📺 UNISECO Project

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This leaflet represents the views of the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

PARTNERS

UNDERSTANDING AND IMPROVING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRO-ECOLOGICAL FARMING SYSTEMS IN THE EU

Strengthening the sustainability of EU farming systems, through co-constructing improved and practice-validated strategies and incentives for the promotion of improved agro-ecological approaches

English language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 2 -

German language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 1 -

Länder, in denen in partizipativen Fallstudien das methodische Instrumentarium des UNISECO Projektes zur Bewertung der ökologischen, wirtschaftlichen und sozialen Auswirkungen innovativer Strategien und Anreize für agrarökologische Ansätze getestet wird:

KOORDINATOR

KONTAKT

Dr. Gerald Schwarz
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Thünen Institute
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MÖGLICHKEITEN SICH ZU BETEILIGEN

- ◆ Teilnahme an nationalen Workshops
- ◆ Beteiligung an den Fallstudien
- ◆ Mitwirken in dem virtuellen Multi-Akteurs-Forum (MAP-NEF)

DEM PROJEKT FOLGEN

UNISECO & Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub
<https://uniseco-project.eu>

Melden Sie sich für unseren Newsletter an und folgen Sie unseren Social Media Kanälen!

🐦 @ProjectUniseco
🌐 UNISECO Project

 Das Projekt wird durch das H2020 Rahmenprogramm der Europäischen Union für Forschung und Innovation unter der Finanzhilfenvereinbarung Nr. 773901 gefördert.

Dieser Flyer repräsentiert die Ansichten der Autoren. Die Europäische Kommission ist nicht für die Verwendung der darin enthaltenen Informationen verantwortlich.

ANALYSE UND VERBESSERUNG DER NACHHALTIGKEIT
VON AGRARÖKOLOGISCHEN
LANDNUTZUNGSSYSTEMEN IN DER EU

Stärkung der Nachhaltigkeit der europäischen Landwirtschaft durch die partizipative Entwicklung verbesserter und praxiserprobter agrarökologischer Strategien, und die Erarbeitung effektiver Anreize zur Förderung agrarökologischer Ansätze.

PARTNER

German language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 2 -

<h3>HINTERGRUND</h3> <p>Die Landwirtschaft steht vor der Herausforderung, Nahrungsmittel und Biomasse wirtschaftlich zu erzeugen und gleichzeitig die Qualität von Boden, Wasser sowie die Biodiversität zu erhalten, die für die Sicherstellung von Ökosystemdienstleistungen erforderlich sind.</p> <p>Hierzu werden agrarökologische Ansätze zunehmend als Alternative zu konventionellen Systemen der Landwirtschaft diskutiert. Es ist zwar allgemein anerkannt, dass agrarökologische Ansätze im Vergleich zu konventioneller Landwirtschaft mehr Wissen und Arbeit pro Hektar erfordern. Allerdings bedarf es eines besseren Verständnisses der sozioökonomischen und politischen Faktoren, welche die Entwicklung und Implementierung agrarökologischer Ansätze behindern oder fördern.</p>	<h3>WAS SIND DIE HERAUSFORDERUNGEN?</h3> <p>Wie können öffentliche Güter bereitgestellt und gleichzeitig eine wirtschaftliche Produktion von privaten Gütern ermöglicht werden?</p> <p>Wie kann die wirtschaftliche und soziale Nachhaltigkeit auf betrieblicher Ebene sichergestellt werden, ohne von öffentlichen Mitteln abhängig zu sein?</p>	<h3>VORGEHENSWEISE</h3> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Analyse von Treibern und Barrieren für die Entwicklung und Implementierung agrarökologischer Ansätze b) Durchführung von partizipativen Fallstudien in 15 europäischen Ländern zur Ableitung und Bewertung von innovativen Managementstrategien und Politik- und Marktanreizen für agrarökologische Landnutzungssysteme c) Biophysikalische und sozioökonomische Modellierung und Entwicklung robuster Indikatoren für die Bewertung der Nachhaltigkeit agrarökologischer Landnutzungssysteme d) Entwicklung und Erprobung eines methodischen Instrumentariums zur Bewertung der Auswirkungen von Managementstrategien, Politik- und Marktanreizen zur Förderung agrarökologischer Landnutzungssysteme in Europa 	
<h3>HINTERGRUND</h3>	<p>1 Entwicklung und Operationalisierung eines konzeptionellen Rahmens sozial-ökologischer Systeme für die die Nachhaltigkeitsbewertung von agrarökologischen Anbausystemen.</p>	<p>2 Kritische Überprüfung von Treibern, welche die Umsetzung agrarökologischer Ansätze in EU Landnutzungssystemen behindern oder fördern und zu verbesserten Managementstrategien führen können.</p>	<p>3 Entwicklung und Anwendung neuer transdisziplinärer methodischer Ansätze zur verbesserten Bewertung der Nachhaltigkeit agrarökologischer Anbausysteme.</p>
<h3>PRIMÄRANALYSE</h3>	<p>4 Bewertung der sozialen, wirtschaftlichen und ökologischen Leistung agrarökologischer Anbausysteme im Vergleich zu konventionellen Systemen auf betrieblicher und territorialer Ebene auf Grundlage einer repräsentativen Typologie.</p>	<p>5 Partizipative Gestaltung innovativer Entwicklungsstrategien für agrarökologische Anbausysteme unter Berücksichtigung von Gleichstellungsaspekten, demographischen Aspekten sowie Fallstudien welche die Vielfalt der landwirtschaftlichen Systeme der EU widerspiegeln.</p>	<p>6 Bewertung der territorialen Auswirkungen einer agrarökologischen Landwirtschaft sowie die Hervorhebung ökologischer, wirtschaftlicher und sozialer Synergien und Zielkonflikte auf regionaler, nationaler und EU-Ebene.</p>
<h3>ERGEBNISSE FÜR POLITIK UND PRAXIS</h3>	<p>7 Bewertung der Wirksamkeit von gemeinsam gestalteten innovativen Markt- und Politikanreizen zur Förderung agrarökologischer Anbausysteme, zur Steigerung der Produktivität, der Bereitstellung öffentlicher Güter und der Schaffung von Arbeitsplätzen im Agrarsektor und den ländlichen Gebieten der EU.</p>	<p>8 Machbarkeitsprüfung der praktischen Umsetzung innovativer Markt- und Politikanreize durch Multi-Akteurs-Plattformen in Fallstudien und auf betrieblicher, regionaler, nationaler und EU-Ebene.</p>	<p>9 Verbesserung der Kooperation und des Wissensaustauschs zwischen Endverbrauchern, Stakeholdern und Wissenschaftlern. Empfehlungen für eine wirksame politische Unterstützung zur Beseitigung der Hemmnisse für verbesserte agrarökologische Ansätze.</p>

- ### ANGESTREBTE WIRKUNGEN ?
- Verbessertes methodisches Verständnis zur Bewertung der Nachhaltigkeit agrarökologischer Ansätze
 - Verbesserung der Kooperation und des Wissensaustauschs zur Entwicklung tragfähiger und langfristiger Strategien für nachhaltige Anbausysteme in der EU
 - Gemeinsam entwickelte Marktmechanismen und politische Instrumente zur Bereitstellung öffentlicher Güter durch wirtschaftliche agrarökologische Landnutzungssysteme
 - Verbesserung der Wissensbasis über den agrarökologischen Landbau in der EU für politische Entscheidungsträger auf EU-, nationaler und regionaler Ebene, Berater, Landwirte, Akteure der Wertschöpfungskette und Verbraucher
 - Beiträge zum Reformprozess der GAP nach 2020 in Bezug auf die Umweltpolitik und zur Unterstützung der Schaffung von Arbeitsplätzen im ländlichen Raum

Hungarian language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 1 –

Részvételi esettanulmányokon keresztül teszteljük az agro-ökológiai megközelítések elősegítésére kidolgozandó innovatív stratégiák és ösztönzők környezeti, gazdasági és társadalmi hatásainak értékelésére szolgáló UNISECO módszertani eszköztárat a következő országokban:

PARTNEREK

KOORDINÁLÓ INTÉZMÉNY

KAPCSOLAT

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 Bundesallee 63 38116 Braunschweig
 NÉMETORSZÁG

VEGYEN RÉSZT ÖN IS!

- ☞ Vegyen részt a nemzeti műhelybeszélgetésekben
- ☞ Vegyen részt az esettanulmányokban
- ☞ Vegyen részt a virtuális Multi-Aktor Platform online közösségünkben (MAP-NEF)

KÖVESSEN BENNÜNKET!

UNISECO honlap és Agro-ökológiai Tudás Központ
<https://uniseco-project.eu>

 UNISECO Project
 UNISECO Project

Íratkozzon fel a rendszeres hírlevelünkre és kövessen bennünket közösségi média csatornáinkon!

 A projekt támogatást kapott az Európai Unió Horizont 2020 kutatási és innovációs programja keretében. Támogatási szerződés száma: N° 773901.

A szöveg a szerzők nevével készült. Az Európai Bizottság nem felelős a dokumentumban szereplő információk használatából eredő következményekért.

AZ AGRO-ÖKOLÓGIAI GAZDÁLKODÁSI RENDSZEREK FENNTARTHATÓSÁGÁNAK MEGÉRTESE ÉS FEJLESZTÉSE AZ EU-BAN

A gazdálkodási rendszerek fenntarthatóságának erősítése az Európai Unióban az agro-ökológiai megközelítések elősegítésére az érintettekkel közösen kialakított, gyakorlat által igazolt stratégiák és ösztönzők révén

Hungarian language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 2 -

<h3 style="text-align: center;">HONNAN EZ A TÉMA?</h3> <p>Napjainkban egyre erősödik az a felismerés, hogy a talaj, a vizek és a biodiverzitás - tehát a környezeti kőzjakavak - megőrzése mellett az emberiségnek szükséges mennyiségű élelmiszer és biomassza megtermelése jelentette kihívást lehetetlen megoldani a jelenleg széles körben uralkodó konvencionális mezőgazdálkodási formákkal.</p> <p>Az agro-ökológiai megközelítések és az ún. öko-funkcionális intenzifikáció alapvetőnek tekinthetők a jövő fenntartható élelmenterelése szempontjából. A nemzeti és nemzetközi erőfeszítések ellenére a kőzjakavak és piaci/magánjakavak együttes előállítása nincsen egyensúlyban, és gyakran nem fenntartható sem üzemi szinten, sem pedig a gazdálkodási rendszerek szintjén.</p>	<h3 style="text-align: center;">MELYEK A KUTATÁST ÉLETRE HÍVÓ KULCSKÉRDÉSEK?</h3> <p style="text-align: center;">Hogyan termelhetők kőzjakavak úgy, hogy közben a magánjakavak termelése is életképes legyen?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Hogyan biztosítható a gazdasági és társadalmi fenntarthatóság üzemi szinten anélkül, hogy túlzottan függne a gazdálkodás a támogatásoktól?</p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">MIRŐL SZÓL AZ UNISECO PROJEKT?</h3> <p>Az UNISECO projekt elősegíti az agro-ökológiai megközelítések gazdálkodási rendszerekben történő megvalósítását és továbbfejlesztését elősegítő vagy éppen gátló gazdasági-társadalmi és szakpolitikai tényezők megértését. A projekt azonosítja és elősegíti a hatékonyabb és hathatósabb európai mezőgazdasági fejlődési stratégiákat figyelembe véve azok sokféleségét.</p>	<h3 style="text-align: center;">MIKÉNT FOGJUK ELÉRNI A KITŰZÖTT PROJEKT CÉLOKAT?</h3> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) áttekintjük az agro-ökológiai megközelítések gátló- és hajtótényezőit, ezek alapján részvételi forgatókönyveket készítünk b) empirikus adatgyűjtést végzünk a részvételi technikákon alapuló esettanulmányokban, közös tudásmegosztáson alapuló innovatív menedzsment stratégiákat és ösztönzőket dolgozunk ki az érintettekkel c) modern természetföldrajzi és gazdasági-társadalmi modellekkel, robusztus indikátorokkal értékeljük az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerek fenntarthatóságát d) módszertani eszköztár fejlesztésével értékeljük az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszereket támogató menedzsment stratégiákat és európai szinten értékeljük az ezeket ösztönző piaci és szakpolitikai intézkedések hatásait 	
ALTYÁMASZTÁS	<p>1 Az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerek fenntarthatósági értékeléséhez a társadalmi-ökológiai rendszer koncepcionális keretének kialakítása és működésbe hozása.</p>	<p>2 Azon tényezők kutatása, amelyek hátráltatják vagy elősegítik az agro-ökológiai megközelítések EU gazdálkodási rendszerekben történő sikeres alkalmazását, amelyek jobb menedzsment stratégiákhoz vezetnek.</p>	<p>3 Új transzdiszciplináris módszertani megközelítések fejlesztése és tesztelése az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerek fenntarthatósági értékelésének jobbításához.</p>
ELSŐDLEGES ELLENVZÉS	<p>4 Az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerek társadalmi, gazdasági és környezeti teljesítményeinek értékelése a konvencionális rendszerekhez képest, üzemi, üzemi-csoport és térségi szinteken, reprezentatív tipológia alapján.</p>	<p>5 Az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerek innovatív fejlesztési stratégiáinak közös kidolgozása, tekintettel a nemek részvételére és a gazdálkodói demográfiára, valamint mindezek értékelése az EU gazdálkodási rendszereinek sokfélesége közepette.</p>	<p>6 Az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodás kiterjesztése megvalósításának térségi szintű fenntarthatósági hatásainak értékelése. a környezeti, gazdasági és társadalmi szinergiák és kompromisszumok azonosítása regionális, nemzeti és EU szinteken.</p>
SZAKPOLITIKA ÉS GYAKORLAT ORIENTÁLT EREDMÉNYEK	<p>7 Az érintettek bevonásával kidolgozott agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszereket támogató innovatív piaci és szakpolitikai ösztönzők többszempontú értékelése az EU-ban: a termelékenység növelése, munkahelyteremtés az agrárszektorban és vidéki térségekben.</p>	<p>8 Az innovatív piaci és szakpolitikai ösztönzők gyakorlati bevezetésének alkalmazás vizsgálata esettanulmányokban üzemi, regionális, nemzeti és EU szinteken.</p>	<p>9 Az érintettek körében kapacitás és tudásmegosztás, az agro-ökológiai megközelítések továbbfejlesztési akadályainak lebontása, valamint az agro-ökológiai gazdálkodást támogató hatékonyabb szakpolitikák megalapozása érdekében.</p>

MELYEK A PROJEKT VÁRHATÓ HATASAI?

- javuló módszertani kapacitás az agro-ökológiai megközelítések fenntarthatóságának értékelésében
- továbbfejlesztett integrált kapacitás és tudásmegosztás a fenntartható európai gazdálkodási rendszerek hosszú távon életképes stratégiáinak kialakításához
- érintettekkel együtt kialakított új és hatékony piaci mechanizmusok, és szakpolitikai eszközök a gazdaságilag életképes agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási rendszerekben keresztli kőzjakav előállításához
- továbbfejlesztett agro-ökológiai gazdálkodási tudásbázis az EU-ban, EU-, nemzeti- és regionális szintű szakpolitikai döntéshozóknak, értéklánc szereplőknek és fogyasztóknak
- a KAP 2020 utáni reformfolyamathoz információ biztosítása, a környezetvédelmi szakpolitikák és vidéki munkahelyteremtési politikák terén

Italian language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 1 -

Paesi in cui saranno realizzati i casi di studio partecipativi per verificare sul campo gli strumenti metodologici di valutazione degli impatti ambientali, economici e sociali delle strategie innovative e degli incentivi per gli approcci agroecologici:

COORDINATO DA **THÜNEN**

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COME PARTECIPARE

- 🌀 Workshop nazionali
- 🌀 Casi studio
- 🌀 Piattaforma multi-attore on-line

SEGUICI

UNISECO & Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub
<https://uniseco-project.eu>

Iscriviti alla newsletter e seguici sui social media!

- 🐦 UNISECO Project
- 🌐 UNISECO Project

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Questo documento riflette il punto di vista degli autori. La Commissione Europea non è responsabile dell'uso che potrebbe essere fatto delle informazioni in esso contenute.

 UNISECO

COMPRENDERE E MIGLIORARE LA SOSTENIBILITÀ
 DEI SISTEMI AGRO-ECOLOGICI NELL'UNIONE EUROPEA

**Rafforzare la sostenibilità
 dei sistemi agricoli dell'UE,
 attraverso la co-costruzione
 di strategie e incentivi
 per la promozione
 di approcci agro-ecologici**

PARTNERS

Italian language version of the UNSIECO leaflet, side 2 –

PERCHÉ?

Cresce la consapevolezza che le sfide legate alla produzione di una quantità sufficiente di cibo e di biomassa e al mantenimento della fertilità dei suoli, della tutela delle risorse idriche e della biodiversità non possono essere risolte solo dai modelli di agricoltura convenzionale attualmente dominanti.

Gli approcci agro-ecologici e l'intensificazione eco-funzionale sono fondamentali per una produzione alimentare sostenibile. Tuttavia, nonostante i notevoli sforzi compiuti a livello internazionale e nazionale, la produzione combinata di beni pubblici e di beni di mercato/privati non è equilibrata, e spesso non è sostenibile né a livello aziendale, né a livello di sistema agricolo nel suo complesso.

QUALI SONO LE SFIDE PRINCIPALI?

Come fornire beni pubblici attraverso una conveniente produzione di beni privati?

Come assicurare la sostenibilità economica e sociale delle aziende agricole senza essere eccessivamente dipendenti dalle risorse pubbliche?

COME SARANNO RAGGIUNTI GLI OBIETTIVI DEL PROGETTO?

- a) Analizzando i fattori determinanti e gli ostacoli agli approcci agro-ecologici attraverso approcci partecipativi
- b) Raccogliendo dati empirici nei diversi casi di studio, basati sullo scambio di conoscenze tra ricercatori, agricoltori e altri attori locali, per una definizione condivisa di strategie di gestione e di incentivi innovativi
- c) Definendo indicatori solidi ed efficaci per valutare la sostenibilità economica e ambientale dei diversi sistemi agro-ecologici
- d) Applicando metodi innovativi per valutare gli impatti delle diverse strategie di gestione aziendale e dei diversi incentivi, pubblici e privati, che promuovono gli approcci agro-ecologici in Europa promoting AEFS in Europe

IL PROGETTO UNISECO

Il progetto UNISECO analizza i fattori socioeconomici e politici (e gli ostacoli) legati allo sviluppo e all'attuazione di approcci agro-ecologici nei sistemi agricoli dell'UE. Il progetto individuerà e faciliterà le strategie di sviluppo più efficaci ed efficienti per l'agricoltura europea nella diversità dei suoi contesti.

QUALI SONO GLI IMPATTI ATTESI?

- Incremento della capacità metodologica per valutare la sostenibilità degli approcci agro-ecologici
- Miglioramento della capacità integrata e della condivisione delle conoscenze per sviluppare strategie sostenibili a lungo termine per i sistemi agricoli europei
- Co-costruzione di meccanismi di mercato e di sostegno pubblico innovativi ed efficaci per la fornitura di beni pubblici attraverso sistemi agroecologici economicamente redditizi
- Una più estesa conoscenza dell'agricoltura agro-ecologica nell'UE, di cui potranno beneficiare decisori politici a livello europeo, nazionale e regionale, consulenti, agricoltori, i vari attori della filiera alimentare e i consumatori
- Raccomandazioni per il processo di riforma della PAC post 2020, per quanto riguarda gli obiettivi ambientali e sociali, in particolare sulla creazione di posti di lavoro nelle zone rurali

COMPRESIONE	1 Sviluppare e rendere operativo un quadro concettuale di sistemi socio-ecologici per la valutazione della loro sostenibilità	2 Analizzare criticamente i fattori che possono ostacolare o promuovere l'attuazione degli approcci agro-ecologici nei sistemi agricoli dell'UE	3 Sviluppare ed esaminare nuovi approcci metodologici transdisciplinari per migliorare la valutazione della sostenibilità di sistemi agro-ecologici
ANALISI	4 Valutare gli effetti sociali, ambientali ed economici dei sistemi agro-ecologici rispetto a quelli convenzionali a livello aziendale e territoriale, sulla base di tipologie rappresentative di aziende e di sistemi agricoli	5 Co-costruire strategie di sviluppo innovative per i sistemi di agricoltura agro-ecologica, considerando anche questioni di genere, sociali e demografiche che caratterizzano i sistemi agricoli europei	6 Valutare gli impatti della sostenibilità territoriale e seguito di attuazione dell'agricoltura agro-ecologica, evidenziando sinergie e criticità ambientali, economiche e sociali a livello regionale, nazionale e comunitario
RISULTATI	7 Valutare l'efficacia degli incentivi pubblici e privati che promuovono l'agricoltura agro-ecologica per migliorare la produttività, l'offerta di beni pubblici e la creazione di posti di lavoro nel settore agricolo e nelle zone rurali dell'UE	8 Verificare la fattibilità attuativa di efficaci incentivi pubblici, attraverso il coinvolgimento delle aziende agricole e degli altri attori a livello locale, ma anche a livello regionale, nazionale e comunitario	9 Migliorare l'integrazione e la condivisione delle conoscenze tra gli utenti finali, i ricercatori e gli altri stakeholder per superare gli ostacoli che limitano gli approcci agro-ecologici e formulare raccomandazioni per un efficace sostegno pubblico all'agricoltura agro-ecologica

4.19. Project Roll-up Posters (EN, BQ-ES, HU versions)

Three generic roll-up displays have been produced for the UNISECO project, one in each of English, Basque/Spanish and Hungarian, which are illustrated below.

